

ON THE ISSUE OF TEACHING RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN A NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

The language of the specialty has been the subject of discussion and close attention of domestic and foreign scientists for decades. A large number of works are devoted to this problem, and it has been sufficiently researched. The article offers a brief overview of the formation and development of methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language and modern language policy in this area, and provides a brief analysis of existing approaches to the study of the Russian language in non-linguistic universities.

In the sixties of the twentieth century, teaching Russian as a foreign language to students in Uzbekistan was aimed primarily at studying special vocabulary and terminology. However, practice has shown that knowledge and mastery of terminological vocabulary did not further contribute to high-quality professional communication. The peculiarities of structuring special scientific texts in those years were ignored, so special educational literature (textbooks, educational and teaching aids) was developed, focused on several different areas of science.

In the seventies of the twentieth century, when teaching the language of a specialty, special attention was paid to the main types of speech activity, as well as the question of the status and nature of texts in the process of developing and organizing educational material. The conclusion was made about the advisability of going beyond the lexical and grammatical analysis of texts in the specialty, the need to prepare for direct communication in the educational and professional field of activity was argued [5]. A positive aspect was the fact that in those years, the focus on the content of the text in relation to lexical and grammatical features when teaching the production of unprepared oral scientific speech became a priority [4].

Later, in the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language, it is distinguished by specialty. However, in educational literature, texts and exercises compiled on the basis of material taken from natural science disciplines were fragmentary and did not provide systematic knowledge. The adapted texts did not explicate the actual use of lexical units in the syntactic format characteristic of the authentic text of the corresponding specialty.

In the eighties of the twentieth century, in the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language, the structural-semantic

approach to the analysis of scientific texts became a priority. The goal was to develop students' non-linguistic skills in constructing standard speech works. When selecting text material, not only professional orientation was taken into account, but also other parameters, for example, the presence in the text of the studied grammatical means, syntactic structures, etc. Much attention was paid to teaching listening and writing new words.

In the nineties, the methodology focuses on the need for the earliest possible introduction of a professionally oriented training system, as well as a differentiated approach to training. A new approach to teaching the language of specialty/professional discourse was proposed. The author's merit lies in the fact that she was the first to introduce the concept of the architectonics of an engineering text, opening a new stage in the theory of teaching the Russian language as a specialty language. She describes the typical structure of a narrow-profile text in the specialty. Focusing on the structure of the text as a whole, the author proposed to study not individual semantic blocks, but the system as a whole. Having highlighted the main structural components of a narrow-profile text in the specialty, he focused on how important it is to give the student an idea of the structure of the text as a whole. From a methodological point of view, it is important to teach a non-linguistic student to identify a topic, a thematic denotational plan, semantic content, and the main semantic blocks of a text [1].

M. Akhmedova made a significant contribution to the creation of a special methodology for teaching Russian as a foreign language at a non-linguistic university with her fundamental work, which presents a description and characteristic features of the language of specialty. According to the author's point of view, the complex content of the "Language of specialty" aspect implies the following:

- 1) formation and development of speech skills in four types of speech activity;
- 2) mastery of linguistic means specific to such functional-stylistic subsystems as oral scientific speech and scientific style;
- 3) mastering a certain minimum of basic information relevant to a specific specialty in order to achieve the required level of subject competence [3].

Agreeing with the author, we consider it appropriate to add that its interpretation and conceptual approach to the study and description of the language of the specialty remain relevant at the present time.

In modern conditions of university education, we are talking about a qualitatively new stage in the development of methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language in a non-linguistic university.

If in the second half of the twentieth century, teaching Russian as a foreign language was focused mainly on reading, translating and understanding special scientific texts taking into account the profile of the university, today there is an increasing need to increase the role of the language component of university education, formed in the context of intercultural communication in the field of professional training future specialists. At the present stage, language education offers a professionally oriented approach to teaching Russian as a foreign language, which is associated with the formation of the ability of professional intercultural communication in foreign students. The trainee is subject to numerous requirements, one of which is the formation of appropriate general cultural and professional competencies, depending on the direction of training of the future specialist.

Taking into account the goals, objectives and requirements presented in the state educational standards of higher education of the third generation, educational programs in Russian as a foreign language for non-linguistic universities, teaching Russian as a foreign language should be professionally oriented. The main goal in preparing a specialist, according to state educational standards of higher education, is for students to acquire the communicative competence necessary for qualified information and creative activities in various fields of professional communication [4]. The essence of professionally oriented training is interaction with special disciplines in order to acquire professional knowledge and develop professionally significant qualities in a foreign student. Russian as a foreign language, being a means of developing professional competence, is an important condition for the successful professional activity of a future specialist who is able to communicate with foreign specialists.

As part of the professional training of a future specialist, it is necessary to develop a mechanism for the formation and development of professional competence based on the assimilation of norms and rules characteristic of the society of the country of the language being studied. In the learning process, in this regard, it is necessary to focus on such professional abilities of the student as:

1) communicative ones, according to which students must be able to choose communication strategies and tactics, interpret and understand representatives of other cultures;

2) linguo-sociocultural, aimed at the use of professionally marked linguistic means in accordance with the norms of the corresponding linguistic culture;

3) interactive, including the ability of the future specialist to carry out professional discourse in accordance with the norms and value orientations characteristic of the professional sphere of a particular linguistic culture [5].

Teaching the language of professional communication based on the development and improvement of linguistic competence helps to improve the quality of specialist training, his ability to communicate effectively and apply professional knowledge in the process of solving specific professional problems, and the development of professional communication skills and abilities. Thus, in the process of teaching a language using modern technologies and modern methodological techniques, the following important task is solved: a foreign student in Russian language classes, in addition to acquiring linguistic/extralinguistic knowledge, must master professional knowledge and general cultural and professional competencies.

Thus, in the process of studying the discipline "Russian Language" at the Tashkent University of Applied Sciences, students must master, in accordance with the requirements of the state educational standard of higher education, the following general cultural and professional competencies:

- ability to communicate orally in Russian to solve problems of interpersonal and intercultural interaction;

- the ability to work in a team, tolerantly perceive social, ethnic, religious and cultural differences;

- the ability to organize and maintain connections with business partners, using systems for collecting the necessary information to expand external relations and exchange experience in the implementation of projects aimed at developing the organization [3].

To successfully complete the task of teaching professional communication in the classroom, it is necessary, first of all, to rely on a professionally oriented text - professional discourse.

In modern scientific literature, a large number of studies are devoted to the study of discourse, which indicate increased interest, in particular, in the processes of generating discourse. In this study, discourse is understood as verbalized speech-cognitive activity, implemented in an integral speech work, including not only linguistic, but also extralinguistic components. Discourse has two components:

- 1) the information transmitted and the means of expressing this transmission;
- 2) surrounding context (knowledge about the situation, which may include social, cultural and another knowledge about the world). Context, as a significant component of any discourse, focuses attention on the communication situation, namely, on the pragmatic component. Discourse is organized according to certain rules characteristic of each specific language. Therefore, when teaching Russian discourse, it is necessary to remember the Russian discursive features of a Russian-language special text and ways of structuring it [4].

The text, acting as the highest communicative unit of training, is presented in practice at all stages of vocational training. Based on mastering terminological vocabulary, special concepts and their comparison in one's own and foreign culture, in the process of teaching Russian as a foreign language, the task of developing professional competence is realized. Professional discourse, being the main means of forming and developing the discursive competence of foreign students, is aimed at acquiring linguistic, speech and extralinguistic knowledge by students and developing the skills necessary for communication in the field of professional communication. In the process of teaching students professional discourse, an authentic text is of fundamental importance, work with which contributes, along with the development of communicative and linguistic competence, to the formation of the ability to creatively process the studied professional information, the development of analysis skills and argumentation in Russian, i.e. formation of discursive skills and discursive competence.

Thus, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- 1) currently there is a change in the educational paradigm in domestic higher educational institutions: today it is aimed at professionally oriented and competency-based approaches, and therefore new requirements are imposed on the level of training of future specialists who, in addition to mastering a complex of knowledge, relevant skills and abilities, must possess certain general cultural and professional competencies;

- 2) a fundamental role in the implementation of the assigned tasks is played by teaching Russian as a foreign language to bachelor students in the language of their specialty on the basis of professional discourse, which pursues the goal of developing the skills and abilities necessary for the implementation of oral and written communication in the field of professional communication, and is the main means of developing and development of discursive competence.

The article made an attempt to highlight only some of the approaches to teaching the Russian language to non-linguistic students in recent decades and to briefly present the language situation in this area at the present stage.

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